
BC-SIM-TN-003

Reports and Note Layout and Flow

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Change Log

Issue	Revision	Date	Affected Pages	Change description

1 Introduction

1.1 Scope

In this document, we will describe the name convention, the format, the flow of reports, notes, and plans produced for the Spectrometers and Imagers for MPO BepiColombo Integrated Observatory SYSTEM (SIMBIO-SYS). A template is attached to this document.

1.2 Acronyms

ASW	Application SoftWare
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
FOP	Flight Operation Plan.
HK	Housekeeping
HRIC	High spatial Resolution Imaging Channel
PI	Principal Investigator
ME	Main Electronics
OA	Open Access
PDOR	Payload Direct Operation Request
PE	Proximity Electronics
PL	Planning Report
SIMBIO-SYS	Spectrometers and Imagers for MPO BepiColombo Integrated Observatory SYSTEM
STC	STereo imaging Channel
TC	Telecommand
TM	Telemetry
TN	Technical Note
TR	Technical Report
UM	User Manual
VIHI	VIsible and Hyper-spectral Imaging channel

2 Name Convention

The document name will be created using the following template: **BC-SIM-YY-XXX**.

YY is an alphabetical code for the document collection from the list below:

LI: Lists of sheets that collect relevant information,

MN: minutes of internal meetings,

PL: documents for the planned test, phase or campaign of observation,

TN: technical notes,

TR: technical report,

UM: user manual of software or tool that will be distributed to the team,

XXX is the progressive number of each collection. The author will contact the archive manager, Romolo Politi (romolo.politi@inaf.it), to obtain the last free progressive number.

3 Cover Pages

The new cover page is designed to identify the document type not only by the name but also by the page's color itself. Follow a table of the primary document types and the associated color.

Document type	Description	Color
LI - MN	List of items, Minutes	Grey
PL	Planning document	Yellow
TN	Technical Note	Blue
TR	Technical Report	Orange
UM	User Manual	Green

4 Authors list

The definition of the list of authors is defined in coordination with the Instrument PI and Co-PIs. The authors are divided into two groups:

1. the first group is formed by the editors of the document whose name order reflect the entity of the respective contribution,
2. the second group contains all the Co-PIs strictly in alphabetical order and ends with the PI.

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ZENODO community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/?p=SIMBIO-SYS>) and in **Section 4.03** of the INAF Open Access repository (<https://openaccess.inaf.it>).

At the end of the submission process, the first author will contact Cristina Re (cristina.re@inaf.it) for the update on the ESA webpage.

The delivery to the ZENODO and OA Archives of any kind of software and related UM, e.g. ASW, reduction and calibration pipelines, analysis tools, etc., must be discussed case by case.

9 Document Versioning

All the documents must have three customized properties:

- Issue, version number of the document;
- Revision, subversion number of the document;
- DOI, unique identifier of the document.

That information will be reported into the page header automatically.

The Title and the subtitle of the document, as well as the first author must be reported in the document info. The version number must be added to the title, starting from version 2. The author can also add the delivery date to the file name.